

Our research

In the ANGIE project, we are developing a novel approach for treating strokes. By magnetically steering microrobots to the clot, we can deliver rtPA directly to the stroke site. This approach allows us to deliver higher concentrations of rtPA directly to the clot, while reducing the overall amount of rtPA used by a factor of 10.000.

Steerable wireless nanodevices

The ANGIE project will develop magnetically steerable wireless nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents via the body's vascular system. Our project will increase health professionals' capacity to treat multiple chronic diseases. Moreover, it will enable doctors to deliver drugs precisely where needed with minimal side effects.

Future Perspectives

The ANGIE technology will allow the blood clots to be dissolved more quickly, enlarges the treatment window and reduces the side effects of the treatment. We hope that this will increase the patients' quality of life and reduce deaths and disabilities caused by strokes.

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Our consortium

ETH Zurich, Switzerland

University of Würzburg, Germany

University of Barcelona, Spain

University of Crete, Greece

Stroke Alliance For Europe, Belgium

Verhaert Masters In Innovation, Belgium

Experian LDA, Portugal

MagnebotiX AG, Switzerland

Discovery Foundation, Greece

ANGIE Interdisciplinary Working Groups

We are building an interdisciplinary community around targeted drug delivery in clinical environment regarding education, gender differences, long-term implications, and potential future returns in societal/ economic innovation and market creation.

ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem

We are creating an innovation ecosystem around the ANGIE technology to foster its take-up in the clinical environments. We bring together health professionals, researchers, entrepreneurs and manufacturers providing them with online courses and technical workshops to understand the innovation aspects of our new technology.

